
**Academic Traditional Library Services Partially Turn To Digital Library
Services: In 21st Century Era**

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Abstract:

The development in (Information Communication Technology) ICT users demand ICT-based library services. Academic libraries implement ICT to satisfy user's demands and provide ICT-based library services to users Academic libraries provide digital reference services, Bibliographic instruction (IB), e-resources access and uses, and Digital innovative library services to users. This paper study on various digital library services provides in 21st Century Era. This paper also studies on role of academic librarians in 21st Century Era.

Keywords: *Digital library services, 21st Century Era, Academic Library.*

Introduction:

The 21st Century Era has brought a revolution in the education system. The mode of education has fully transferred from blackboard to desktop. Academic libraries also accept this challenge and provide digital library services to their users. With the development in ICT academic libraries have already implemented this technology and provide some digital library services to users. Now academic libraries have opportunities to marketing and awareness of these digital library services in users and to change their attitude towards the libraries.

Digital library and Services:

A digital library is an online database of digital objects that can include text, still images, audio, video, digital documents, or other digital media formats. Objects can consist of digitized content like print or photographs as well as originally

produced digital content like word processor files or social media posts. In addition to storing content, digital libraries provide means for organizing, searching, and retrieving the content contained in the collection. Today digital libraries have improved library services like electronic journal support service, Electronic Document Delivery, Electronic Publishing, Resource Service, Inter-Library Loan, full-text searching, cross-searching specialist abstracting and indexing databases etc. for learning, teaching and research.

According to Gladney H.M, et. Al. (1994):

“A digital library service is an assemblage of digital computing, storage, and communications machinery together with the software needed to reproduce, emulate, and extend the services provided by conventional libraries based on paper and other material means of collecting, storing,

cataloguing, finding, and disseminating information.”

These services can be broadly categorized

- 1) Digital reference services
- 2) Bibliographic instructions (BI),
- 3) E-resource access and uses
- 4) Digital services initiatives.

1) Digital Reference Services:

One of the most significant achievements in the information and communication sector is the introduction of advanced communication network i.e., the internet, the technology connecting a computer with Millions of computers in the network. In the field of library and information science, the Internet has become one of the most popular and talked about subject. With the help of internet academic libraries can easily provide digital reference services to their users.

Digital Reference model divide into two types by (Francoeur, 2002 and Berube, 2003).

A. Asynchronous Transactions:

An asynchronous transaction involves time delay between the question and answer. Some asynchronous transactions are following

Email Services: Email is most useful tool for online information delivery. User send their reference queries to library. Librarians have solved this reference queries through the e- resources available with him.

Web forum Services: Web forum first found in UK public libraries. Library has designed a website webpage. In this webpage user can insert query or questions. The query has received in structured form

and librarian solves this query through email.

Ask Librarian Services: This service is useful for academic libraries. With the library website libraries allow users to ask questions and received answers for free from public information located mainly on the World Wide Web or from proprietary databases and networks of field experts.

B. Synchronous Transactions:

Synchronous transaction involves real time in which immediate response to the query. Some following synchronous transactions are following-

Text Based Chat Services: Academic libraries can implement this library services. With the help of chat and instant massaging librarian speak with each other in real time on the internet. This chat reference services associated with 24/7. It is very difficult for single librarian. Lib Chat service is best example.

Video-conferencing or Web-cam services: In this service librarian can use face to face communication. Academic libraries can apply these services and solves user query with face to face communication.

Digital Reference Robot: digital reference robot essentially uses artificial intelligence to responds questions. The most well-known of this type of service is Ask jeevs available on internet.

2) Bibliographic Instruction (BI):

Academic libraries are use this services to support in research of students and faculty. In this service instructional programs designed to teach library users how to locate the information they need quickly and effectively. BI usually covers the library’s system of organizing materials,

the structure of the literature of the field, research methodologies appropriate to the discipline, and specific resources and finding tools (catalogs, indexes and abstracting services, bibliographic databases, etc.)

3) E-resources access and Uses:

1. Access to electronic reference books and textbooks (Special subjects or Multidisciplinary subjects) – Academic libraries are focused on improve collection of e-resources. Now academic libraries are need balanced collections of prints as well as e-resources for best services provides to users.
2. Access to electronic databases. – Academic libraries trying to subscribe databases. It will help enhance e-resources of library.
3. Access to electronic journals. – Subject oriented journals for faculty and students subscribes by library enhance subject knowledge.

Open Access Institutional Repository:

Open-access repository for the scholarly works, research, publications, creative activities, newsletter, and reports produced for faculty, students and staff publish their electronic guide on the Internet, which will lead to attracting and boosting the number of users’.

4) Digital Services Initiatives:

- a) Organized online library orientation, workshop and book exhibition.
- b) Organized online reading and discussion groups.
- c) Provide the public health awareness and update information.

Role of Librarian in post 21st Century Era:

1. Adopt ICT Skills:

Academic librarian should have knowledge about webpage design, Installation and customization of software, database managements systems. The academic librarian should aware about various library management software’s like Lybsis, SOUL, Koha, New Gen lib

2. Online Communication Skill:

Awareness of digital library services have been increased. Online communication skills like acceptance of user’s queries and solves this query and reply it. This work will be major part of libraries in coming days.

3. Encourage Library Staff:

Librarians also need motivational skills. It should encourage library staff to adopt various ICT skills for sustain in digital era.

4. Promote Digital Library Services:

Librarian not only introduces new services in library but also promote this services so users can aware it. Initiatives like virtual post card, create virtual post cards for students and share post card on library Facebook page or library twitter.

5. Acquire Necessary Equipment and Software for Providing Digital Library Services:

To provide effective and efficient services to the user, library need high-quality technical equipment and software. Academic librarians should convey to management for acquires this equipment and software in the library.

6. Increase the number of e-resources in the library and increase awareness in students and faculty:

In the 21st century era the demands of e-resources will increase because awareness of these e-resources have been increased. Academic libraries should not only try to focus on print collections but also try to focus on e-resources.

7. Promote digital literacy skills in staff, students and faculty:

Digital library refers to the ability to understand information and perform tasks in digital environments. Librarians should help staff, students and faculty by using computers to find, manipulate and communicate information. Librarian also helps them in identify information in various types of media and formats (such as databases, internet and films).

8. To evaluate, organize and disseminate authentic information with the help of Internet:

There is a lot of information available on the internet. To find out authentic information is not an easy task. The academic librarian should acquire proper knowledge about evaluating, organizing and disseminating authentic information.

9. Make a Social media platform between library and users:

Use of social media is increasing in society. Most students, faculty and research scholars are using social media. The academic librarian should take advantage of this social media and share our library services through social media like Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, LinkedIn etc.

10. Awareness of digital copyright:

Librarian tries to make digital copyright awareness between staff, students, faculty and researchers. Librarians should be aware of licensed e-content. Librarians should take the initiative of fair use of e-content available on the internet.

Conclusion:

Academic libraries focus on digital reference services there are two types of digital reference services. The first one is services provided on real-time and services provide on the delay time. Academic libraries should solve user queries through these types of reference services. Academic libraries also try to create guides book of bibliographic instruction or conduct video lectures through various online platforms like Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft team etc. it helps in research of users. Academic libraries are also increase their e-resources collections and provide to users through user id based. Academic libraries also innovate new digital services for the satisfaction of user information needs.

References:

1. Gladney H.M, et. Al. (1994) Digital library: Gross structure and requirements: Report from a workshop. IBM Research Report, RJ 9840, May 1994.
2. Akintola B.A., & Olayiwola, I.B. (2004). Academic libraries: The Internet and its potential impact on teaching and learning in Nigerian tertiary institutions. *Journal of Library and Information Science* 1 (1&2): 34-46
3. Bakker, T (2002). Virtual reference services: Connecting users with

- experts and supporting the development of skills. *Liber Quarterly*, Vol 12, pp. 124-137
4. Mahesh, G., & Mittal, R. (2008). *Digital Libraries in India: A Review*. *Libri*, 58. <https://doi.org/10.1515/libr.2008.002> (accessed on 10 July 2020)
 5. Schwartz, C. (2000). Digital libraries: An overview. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 26(6), 385–393. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0099-1333\(00\)00159-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0099-1333(00)00159-2) (accessed on 10 July 2020)
 6. Oluwabiyi, M.,O. (2017) Digital reference services: an overview: *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, Vol. 8 (1) Pg 66 – 75. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ijjkm.v8i1.8> (accessed on 11 July 2020)
 7. Obeidat, O. A. (2020). Evaluation Digital Library Services During Covid-19 Pandemic: Using Users' Experiences In Academic Institution, *Jordan*, Vol 6(3).pp39-48, June2020.
 8. Sreenivasulu, V. (2000). 'The role of digital librarian in the management of digital Information systems (DIS)'. *The Electronic Library*, 18(1): 12-20
 9. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_library (accessed on 10 July 2020)